

Actual vs Predicted (MaxUV)

Standardized Residuals (MaxUV)

Partial Regression Plot (MaxUV)

Durbin-Watson Statistic

$$DW = 1.2291$$

Interpretation:

1 = positive autocorrelation

2 = no autocorrelation

4 = negative autocorrelation

Breusch–Pagan Test

LM Statistic: 1.8307

p-value: 0.1760

Conclusion: No Heteroskedasticity

White Test

White Statistic: 2.6414

df: 2

p-value: 0.2669

Conclusion: No Heteroskedasticity

Histogram of Residuals (MaxUV)

P-P Plot (Normality Test) – MaxUV

